

Creation of the first circular economy skate park imagined, designed and created by the inhabitants of the Community of Communes between Dore and Allier in Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes

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Abstract

The FabCity model, shared public space, is an alternative model of social innovation that aims to involve citizens in local production by relying on the dynamics generated by third places.

This project is based on a reflection on the production of urban commons in the public space (here a skatepark), establishing a cross dynamic of cooperation between the local community, the citizen contribution, and the private actors. This experimentation through this common operation, and visible to all, shows that the establishment of the circular economy in a territory can also be the result of a process of contributory democracy and new forms of governance in public policies. The objective of this article is to present the methodology deployed, the local loop of actors created, whose epicenter is the Lezoux Media Library. Through this experiment, we show and describe new forms of innovation in the territories, driven by the FabCity dynamic, with the center of gravity of the contributory dimension of citizens, including a real plurality of actors in design and decision-making.

Keywords

Third place, subsistence territory, data, civic infrastructure

1 Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic has highlighted the vulnerability of our organizations, leading us to think about more agile, more distributed, and more resilient production models in the territories. This manufacturer territory strategy is at the heart of the circular economy model associated with the FabCity. It invites to move from a linear and centralized economic model to a model distributed on the territory for the creation of local productive hubs. However, it is not enough that the local supply is available for the inhabitants to seize it as consumers or producers.

The visibility of local production is a crucial issue. This raises the question of awareness and communication levers around “made in local”, which may involve lifting the veil on the manufacturing chains of products currently consumed locally.

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The promotion of local manufacturing can also encourage a reappropriation of the productive act by the citizen, essential to encourage new vocations and new ideas at the service of the manufacturing territory. We present here the original project to create a skate-park imagined, thought out and created by the inhabitants of the Community of Communes between Dore and Allier in France. This project is betting on involving citizens in local production by relying on a co-innovation approach developed within the third place of the Lezoux Media Library. It therefore positions the citizen no longer in a process of participation but in a process of contribution to the territorial project.

Thus, the third place, the Media Library of Lezoux, becomes a real space of contributory democracy, with tools and services allowing the citizen to imagine their territory of tomorrow and produce common goods. The territory can then be considered as a distributed network of places of production, creation, and services, available in hyper-proximity for the citizen.

We therefore present in the first part the context, the actors involved in the approach, then the co-innovation process and finally the first module of the skate-park.

2 The context

2.1 The context of the experimentation: manufacture the city, contributive city

This project follows on from the “Manufacture de ville – Cité Contributive” program on the Biennale du Design de St-Étienne 2019. Manufacture de la ville is an initiative to revitalize the city center of Saint-Etienne by the inhabitants, accompanied by the Metropolis and the City of Saint Etienne. From existing and identified public spaces (theater, secular homes, social centers, etc.), it was a question with the inhabitants, in a collaborative approach, of rethinking and revitalizing these spaces to invent shared places of life. and contributory (Third Places) producers of projects, innovative services and creating social ties and solidarity between the inhabitants. This project responded to a certain number of intersecting objectives where the citizen becomes the expert of his needs and his uses of the city by reinventing services and producing projects:

- Rebalance the Smart City project (intelligent city) focused on emerging technologies and algorithmic power by claiming the intelligence of the city; contributory city supported by the inhabitants and part of the public spaces and places of the metropolis
- Enable residents to actively participate and contribute to the urban project by being co-constructor of public policies with the community
- Strengthen citizens' ability to act in their neighborhood in the context of the emergence of the collaborative society
- Create social, intergenerational links and interaction between inhabitants in a peaceful city
- Through the intervention of the inhabitants, produce commons that can be shared between all
- Rethink the public space and its appropriation by the inhabitants
- Set up a system of shared and complementary public spaces throughout the urban fabric
- Give the city dweller the opportunity to develop joint projects and share the challenges of the metropolis

This event was an opportunity to prototype a collection of three objects (the crocodile, the whale, and the skunk-bear) called MULO - Mobilier d'Urgence Ludique Open Source. These are urban furniture designed to playfully inhabit a vacant space (wasteland, garden) with and for the inhabitants of the Southeast district of the city of Saint Etienne. Design files are available on the Distributed Manufacturing Platform MakerNet.

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Figure 1: Objects from the MULO collection and creation of the prototype with the inhabitants

3 The actors involved in the experimentation

From this last success, we continued this experiment in Lezoux with the aim of creating a local loop for the production of public facilities with citizens, local designers, local resources and local businesses, in a global approach to circular economy. Lezoux is a small commune in the Puy-de-Dôme department in Auvergne in central France (5 508 inhabitants).

Lezoux has been recognized for many years for its tradition of citizen participation. On this territory resides the only media library in Europe which was imagined, thought out and created by its inhabitants: the Médiathèque of Lezoux. It is a futuristic media library based on a contributory model: “the media library of which you are the hero”. This third place, unique in France, evolves daily by highlighting the resources, know-how, knowledge and passions of users and the territory. It is a real third place, where the citizen participates: he is not a simple consumer of cultural goods, he brings know-how, knowledge, and he creates something common.

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The Mediathèque of Lezoux (<https://www.mediatheques-entre-dore-et-allier.fr/>) is a third place which puts in synergy the following actors:

- The young people, citizens of the city of Lezoux who imagined the constituent elements of the sliding space. The project was born from the initiative of the teenagers of the territory, who wish to build a space in their image to practice sliding sports in complete safety. The skate-park must be a friendly place for exchanges but also flexible and mobile, which can be moved to the different spaces of the city.
- Local officials
- local corporations to identify the shapes, contours and new technologies associated with the future project.
- The “Banque des Territoires”

The Banque des Territoires (Bank of Territories, <https://www.banquedesterritoires.fr/>), organization of the French Government that supports public policies and works for economic, social and sustainable development. This institution brings a financial support for this experimentation.

4 Methodology

The experimentation follows the Distributed Design Market Plateform – DDMP - framework.

Figure 2 : DDMP applied to the experiment

The experiment has been done according to the following different steps:

4.1 Description of the subsistence territory

The notion of “subsistence territory” was popularized by the philosopher Bruno Latour. It broadens our understanding of territories by moving from a cartographic and administrative definition (“everything that can be located on a map is made into a territory by surrounding it with a line”) to an “ethological definition: tell me what you live, and I will tell you how far extends your field of life” (Latour,2021). The aim is not to have the most objective photograph possible of what is inside a perimeter, but to draw up a "list of interactions with those on whom we depend", whoever they are and wherever they are. For this, Bruno

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Latour underlines the importance of multi-scale description work, at the crossroads between the individual and the collective, to observe the networked geography that emerges. The data participate in this work of description of “territories of substance”. It makes it possible to express the productive heritage of the territory, the basis for the synergy of the actors.

4.2 Co-conception

For eight months, a series of collaborative workshops took place at the third place Médiathèque de Lezoux. The workshops aim to:

- Create a group of mobilized citizens
- reveal the expectations and needs of the inhabitants
- Co-construct with citizens the specifications of the different units of the skatepark
- Co-construct with citizens the design plans for one or more units of the skatepark

These workshops were done in partnership with the community.

4.3 Work with local businesses and recycling units

For 6 months, a series of collaborative workshops with local businesses took place at the third place Médiathèque of Lezoux. The challenge is to support cooperation between territorial businesses. For this, we have to think with hybrid forms to create a FabCity sector of territory with all the actors of the chain, but localized. Thus, the workshops aim to:

- Create a group of local corporations mobilized
- Reveal the waste deposits available in the municipality that can be used in the experiment
- Find local waste reuse solutions
- Create with companies the manufacturing plans of one or more units of the skatepark.

4.4 Prototyping session

A participatory prototyping workshop was proposed within the third place.

4.5 Manufacturing

The manufacture of the skatepark units was entrusted to the companies associated with the process.

5 Results

5.1 Description of the Lezoux subsistence territory

To describe the territories of subsistence is to describe what binds us, what our productive systems depend on. For this, we use the very numerous sources of data associated with the various public policies (Small Towns of Tomorrow, Territory of Industry, INSEE, Pôle Emploi, etc.). From a computer science point of view, territories, whatever their size, can be seen as complex multi-actor, multi-level and multi-process systems. They bring together various actors – communities, companies, citizens... – who produce data, many of which are public and accessible. It is therefore a question of bringing together the internal data modeling of productive structures (qualifying their real productive activity, their resources, their flows, etc.) and the modeling of external data associated with a locality/territory (actors, games actors, objectives, contractualisations, public policies, relations, climate.....). This is the challenge of the Atlas of Productive Resiliency research program that the University of Clermont Auvergne is deploying with the company OpenStudio (website : <https://atlas.productive-synergies.com/>).

The Atlas of Productive Synergies tool makes it possible to build a modeling of the companies/products/locality triptych according to all the information associated with their productive

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know-how, the locality, their manufactured goods associated with productive connections. This modeling is based on the work proposed by teams from Harvard University on modeling the economic complexity of countries. Based on the analysis of trade and observing the exports of each country, it is possible to determine what “the territory knows how to produce” and thus to measure its productive know-how (Pachot, 2021).

This model, called the product-space (Hidalgo,2007), highlights the complementarity of resources and productive skills available at the product level. It provides a measure of relatedness between products. At the level of the Lezoux community, the tool offers the mapping of 19 companies, covering the territory, whose workforce is between 10 and 20 employees. Each company is represented by a circle, the radius of which is weighted by the workforce, and a color corresponding to its sector of activity. The tool analyzes 257 sectors of activity divided into 12 macro-sectors (agriculture/fishing, extractive activities, forestry/woodworking, mineral construction materials, metallurgy, paper/cardboard/printing, chemicals, plastics/rubber). These companies are linked by dotted lines (see Figure 2), expressing the scenarios of productive synergies between establishments.

Figure 3: Example of visualization of the productive actors of the territory of Lezoux

These companies produce goods. The tool offers a visualization of the productive fabric, as here the productive space of the territory of Lezoux (see figure 3), in which each color corresponds to a category of products and the gray points to products not manufactured on the territory. In the product space of the Lezoux territory, we are interested in the following products identified by the codes from international nomenclatures:

- 8112 : Tire waste and scrap
- 4202 : Trunks, suitcases and briefcases
- 6810 : Articles of cement, concrete or artificial stone
- 7010 : Carboys, bottles, flasks, jars, pots, tubular packaging,

This information, provided by data processing, makes it possible to identify the existence of a large deposit of waste from the tire production activity, construction, plastic production.

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5.2 Co-design and prototyping sessions with citizens

The workshops mobilized fifty young people. During these workshops, we used virtual reality technologies as a support for design and citizen consultation for the development of the skatepark space. In concrete terms, we used the Arkio tool, which immerses users in a 3D virtual space like the space to be developed, so that they can imagine it, live an experience and then participate in its development. In this space, the young inhabitants were able to create, move, modify, delete or add elements of the skatepark (bowl, ramp, etc.), and leave comments on the experience or experience of the user journey. The proposals thus allow the choice between several scenarios of layouts of the skatepark space.

5.3 Work with local businesses and recycling units

The definition of the subsistence territory made it possible to identify the following local businesses in the process:

- Procar company collects, sorts and shreds used tyres. Concretely, this company will transform the tires into recyclable shredded material
- Wood&Co specialized in wood construction

But it also highlighted the lack of local actors in capacity to valorize the deposits of shredded tires. To fill this gap, we opted for the solution of deploying an EtNisi micro-factory for processing materials from the company ProCar.

From this raw material of recycled tires, it will be possible to recreate a new, innovative, and unprecedented material, thanks to the EtNisi micro-factory: tire Wasterial®, a material loaded with meaning, emotion and the industrial heritage of the territory. from the Puy de Dome. The Wasterial® tire is the contraction of "Waste" for waste and "material" for matter. It is therefore a new innovative and sustainable material, made up of 75% recycled materials, resulting from the agglomeration of shredded and crushed tires with a binder chosen to create resistant materials, for paving, tiling, furniture or even street furniture.

5.4 Industrial production

This phase is currently underway. The first modules of the skatepark are in the production phase with the local companies mentioned.

6 Conclusion

The FabCity approach developed here in Lezoux around the third place the Médiathèque of Lezoux has enabled the creation of a new community of actors around the creation of a local loop for the production

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of public facilities with citizens, local designers and local factories. The approach will have made it possible to bring out the innovative creation of a new material, the Wasterial of tires resulting from the recycling of tire waste. It is also a change of posture. It is a question here of thinking beyond the local in order to develop a more systemic thought which goes beyond the borders of the territory of action in which the habitus fit. The advantages would be multiple:

- At the societal level, such an experiment would raise awareness of urban commons and citizen participation.
- Such an experiment would constitute support for the local economy, a time for citizen mobilization around local production in a circular economy dynamic.

The local loop of actors created, whose epicenter is the Media Library Médiathèque of Lezoux, is the expression of the new forms of innovation on the territories, carried by the FabCity dynamic, with as a center of gravity the contributive dimension of the citizens, including a true plurality of actors in the conception and the decision.

References

Latour, B. (2021). *After the Lockdown a Metamorphosis*, Duke Polity Press

Pachot A., Albouy-Kissi A., Albouy-Kissi B., Chausse F., (2021) Multiobjective recommendation for sustainable production systems, MORS workshop held in conjunction with the 15th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems (RecSys)

Hidalgo, C.A., et al., 2007. [The Product Space Conditions the Development of Nations](#). *Science*, 317 (5837), pp. 482-487.